

The foot, cubit, metre, and φ , π and e

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Abstract

A short document highlighting the consistent relationship between the foot, cubit and metre, and combinations of them, and phi, pi and e, via $e-1$.

Keywords: Egyptology, metrology, royal cubit, cubit, metre, foot, metric system, ancient measures

Contents

1. Introduction
2. Units
3. The ratios
4. Discussion
5. Thanks
6. Bibliography

1. Introduction

This was originally going to be an aside in another paper I am working on, but I thought it was interesting and important enough to have its own space.

I refer the reader to my other paper [1] about the cubit and accept it as read, so that I don't have to repeat that content here. That paper will be updated shortly to bring it in line with this one.

2. Units

Instead of thinking of π , φ and e as ratios or irrational numbers, rather think of them as lengths. In particular, as lengths on the circumference of a 1-metre diameter circle.

There is a practical limit to how accurately we can, or indeed need to, measure a line. For a 1 metre diameter circle, we would not be able to measure or draw a circumference more accurately than 3.1416 m long, given the limitations of pencil, ruler, and our eyes. We can thus say, that for practical purposes, π is 3.1416m. Similarly, we can peg φ at 1.618m, φ^2 at 2.618m, and e at 2.7183m.

That allows us to define our units and symbols.

Name	Symbol	Pragmatic value (metres)
Archimedes' constant	π	3.1416
Euler's number	e	2.7183
$e - 1$	\acute{e}	1.7183
Golden ratio	φ	1.618
Royal cubit	\mathbb{C}	0.5236 (from $\pi/6$)
Metre	m	1.0000
Grand metre (five feet)	M	$1.5236 = 1\text{m} + 1\mathbb{C}$
Foot, Imperial	f	0.3047 (0.30472 would be better)
Nby-rod	N	$0.6732 = 1\mathbb{C} + \text{double-palm}$
"Megalithic yard"	Y	$0.8283 = 1\mathbb{C} + 1\text{f}$
Six feet	S	$1.8283 = 1\text{m} + 1\mathbb{C} + 1\text{f}$

Table 1: Units and values

3. The ratios

Using these four-decimal values, with answers also rounded to four places, we then have

$$\frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\varphi^2}{5} = \pi - \varphi^2 = \mathbb{C}$$

$$\frac{1+\pi}{e} = \frac{\varphi^2}{e-1} = \pi - \varphi = \mathbb{C} + 1 = \text{M}$$

$$\frac{\text{M}}{5} = \frac{\text{M}+\text{f}}{6} = \text{f} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\text{m}+\mathbb{C}}{5} = \frac{\text{m}+\mathbb{C}+\text{f}}{6} = \text{f}$$

Alan Green points out [2] that the ratio between \mathbb{C} and f is \acute{e} (i.e. $e-1$). Green also points out that \acute{e} represents the "growth" on the initial investment of 1, in the classical interest calculation.

The problem with the foot is that it is currently "defined" as 0.3048m, presumably so that one inch is a two decimals (2.54cm) rather than a longer string of decimals in metric, like it was 100 years ago. Here is a scan from Chambers English Dictionary, from circa 1937:

BRITISH LINEAL MEASURES. &c. = FRENCH.

<i>British.</i> L I N E A L.	<i>French.</i>
Inch.....	25.399 millimètres.
Foot.....	30.479 centimètres.
Yard.....	0.914 mètre.
Chain [22 yards].....	20.116 mètres.
Furlong [10 chains]....	201.164 "
Mile.....	1.609 kilomètre.....5 miles = 8 kilomètres, nearly.

If we multiply 25.399mm by 12, we get 30.4788cm rather than the rounded value used above.

The foot has had a chequered history, but I accept that the current value is close to some standard that has managed to be passed down through the ages. I am using 0.3047m rather than the currently defined 0.3048m.

℄/é is 0.30472m (to 5 places) but for the purposes of this exercise we will work with 0.3047, except for the first sum, where the 0.00002 makes a difference due to the relatively low values involved.

The é relationship between ℄ and f. extends beyond them.

There is a persistent and consistent relationship between the famous irrationals and the units of length, which can surely not be co-incidence. Observe:

$$\frac{\mathbb{C}}{f} \approx \frac{e\mathbb{C}}{Y} \approx \frac{\acute{e}}{m} \approx \frac{\varphi^2}{M} \approx \frac{\pi}{S} \approx \acute{e} \approx 1.7183$$

Item	Denominator Lengths	Calculation	Result	Result 2
℄ / f	foot	0.5236 / 0.30472	1.7183	1.72
e℄ / Y	cubit + foot	(2.7183 * 0.5236) / 0.8283	1.7183	1.72
é / m	metre	1.7183 / 1.0000	1.7183	1.72
φ ² / M	metre + cubit	2.618 / 1.5236	1.7183	1.72
π / S	metre + cubit + foot (nby-rod not included above)	3.1416 / 1.8283	1.7183	1.72
π / Ne	nby-rod	3.1416 / (0.6732 · 2.7183)	1.7168	1.72

Table 2: Analysis of e-1 relationships

4. Discussion

As far as I know there is no connection between π, φ, and e (or e-1), yet here we see them connected via units of length, remembering that ℄ itself is π/6 or φ²/5. These relationships partly work because M, which is m + ℄, equates to 5 feet.

π, φ, and e are not just any irrationals, but arguably the three most important.

[Some may argue that √2 is more important than φ, but whoever designed the cubit system and built Giza seems to have put φ on par with π, if not even higher.]

As shown above, they are linked to arguably the three most important units of length in human history, which should have nothing to do with them, by conventional wisdom. The relationship becomes even more mysterious if we try to reconcile the accepted timeline and origins of the irrationals and these lengths, given the interplay between them.

5. Thanks

Thanks as always to my “guides,” whoever or whatever they are, for their constant prompting and odd ideas which frequently lead to shocking discoveries and amazed laughter. I wish I knew them.

6. Bibliography

- [1] Douglas, Ian, ‘The Beautiful Cubit System’. Jun. 30, 2019, [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3263864>.
- [2] BARDCODE, *CPAK Alan Green Trailer*. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i7qQEJW8K_U.